

CASE REPORT

Off Pump Total Arterial Coronary Revascularization in Dextrocardia with Situs Inversus Totalis: A Case Report

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ABSTRACT

Dextrocardia with situs inversus is a rare entity and if not associated with any congenital heart disorder then these persons lead a normal life. CABG in dextrocardia is technically a challenging task. Here we are reporting a case of off pump total arterial CABG in a patient with dextrocardia with situs inversustotalis with regard to technique and modifications for the surgery.

Key words: dextrocardia, situs inversustotalis, CABG, off pump, congenital, heart.

INTRODUCTION

Dextrocardia is usually associated with congenital heart diseases and if not, then, it behaves normally like levocardia with regard to natural history. Dextrocardia with situs inversus behaves more like normal than dextrocardia with situs solitus.

Coronary artery disease after age 40 year is very common in normal levocardia heart (i.e. apex of heart is on left side with atrial situs and main mass of heart is lying left of the midline) although may occur in younger age group. Dextrocardia is not exception for this yet an uncommon entity.

Dextrocardia is associated with surgical challenges eg, position of surgeon, cannulation for CPB, conduit selection, graft configuration, sequence of anastomosis etc.

Here, we are presenting a case of situs inversustotalis with dextrocardia with TVD in which total arterial revascularization was done off pump.

PATIENT PROFILE

59 year old female presented to us with history of recurrent angina right side of chest radiating to right arm for last 3 years and an episode of acute myocardial

infarction 3 months back. Coronary angiography was done which showed Tripple vessel disease. She was referred to us for surgery.

She was non hypertensive and, non diabetic with no history of other chronic illness.

Patient was thoroughly evaluated with routine blood investigations, viral markers, and covid test. Her chest x-ray (Picture/illustration 1) showed dextrocardia with situs inversus. Liver was under left hemidiaphragm and fundal shadow was under right hemidiaphragm.

HRCT thorax for covid infection was also negative

Electrocardiography (Figure 2) was typical of dextrocardia and Coronary artery disease i.e. inverted P wave with negative QRS deflection in lead I and upright P wave with positive QRS deflection in lead avR and poor progression of R wave in left chest leads.

Findings suggestive of Coronary artery disease were presence of q wave in lead V2, V5, V6, ST depression with T wave inversion in lead V4R, V5R, and V6R.

2D echo (Figure 3) showed situs inversus with dextrocardia with normal chamber dimensions. Superior vena cava and Inferior vena cava were on left side of spine and draining into left side placed Right atrium. Pulmonary veins draining into right sided left atrium. Apex was lying on right side of midline. Morphologic right ventricular was on left side of midline and morphologic left ventricle was on right side of midline. Aorta was lying on right side of spine and ascending aorta was situated on left side of main pulmonary artery with ventriculo arterial concordance. There was grade II left ventricular diastolic dysfunction with normal systolic function (Ejection fraction – 55 %).

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Coronary angiography (Figure 4a,4b,4c,4d) revealed mirror image coronary artery pattern with left arterial system was lying on right side of main mass and right coronary artery was on left side of main mass. There was approximately 95% stenosis in proximal Left anterior descending artery, obtuse marginal 1, proximal right coronary and distal right coronary artery just before crux.

Ultrasonography abdomen confirmed the finding of abdominal situs that is liver was on left side and spleen was on right side.

There was moderate to severe obstructive respiratory dysfunction and both carotid arteries were normal on colour Doppler study.

With negative corona profile and HRCT thorax, patient was taken for surgery.

Her both radial arteries were checked with Allen test for harvesting IMA and Radial artery.

INTRA OPERATIVE PROFILE

ECG electrodes were fixed on back side of right chest wall. Patient was anesthetized with fentanyl, sodium thiopental, and rocuronium and maintained with sevoflurane and intermittent doses of fentanyl and rocuronium. Arterial and venous monitoring lines were placed and urinary catheterization was done.

Chest was opened with midline sternotomy, pericardium was opened and hitched up. Anatomy (Figure 5) of heart was consistent with mirror image pattern with right aortic arch. LAD was situated on right side, OM was on right lateral surface, RCA was on left side, and PDA was situated on inferior wall left side.

After inspection of anatomy, RIMA (Figure 6a,6b,6c), LIMA (Figure 6d,6e), and LEFT RADIAL (Figure 6f) artery were harvested on 1 mg/kg heparin dose with ACT more than 280 seconds. RIMA was used as pedicled graft and LIMA and RADIAL aretery were used as free graft. Patient was heparinized again to achieve ACT more than 300 seconds. Procedure was done off pump and with surgeon standing on right side of the patient. Proximal anastomosis (Figure 7) were done first with LIMA was anastomosed to right lateral surface and RADIAL artery was anastomosed to left anterolateral surface of ascending aorta with 7/0 prolene in continuous manner. Patency was checked.

Stabilizer was fixed on inferior arm of retractor and LAD (Figure 8) was stabilized. Exposure was improved with hitching up the pericardial stay taken in between the right superior and inferior pulmonary vein. A 5/0 prolene control sling was taken around LAD proximal

to the proposed site of anastomosis. Adequate sized LAD arteriotomy was done and shunt of 1.75mm size was placed inside the arteriotomy. RIMA was anastomosed to LAD as pedicled graft with 7/0 prolene in tension free manner. RIMA graft was fixed to epicardium. Now stabilizer was fixed on inferior arm of retractor near its right arm and OM1 artery (Figure 9) was fixed. LIMA was anastomosed to OM1 in similar manner as LAD grafting. For PDA exposure, octopus was stabilized at right arm of retractor near its inferior portion and RADIAL artery was anastomosed to PDA (Figure 10) similarly. Shunt size for OM1 and PDA was 1.5mm.

After completion of the procedure heparin was reversed. Hemodynamically patient's parameters were remain stable throughout the procedure therefore no inotropes were required. Chest was closed in usual manner after inserting bilateral pleural and mediastinal drains. She was shifted to ICU on nitroglycerine infusion.

Postoperative course was uneventful and she was extubated in 6 hrs. Patient was discharged on day 7.

DISCUSSION

Dextrocardia with situs inverses is an unusual congenital abnormality with an incidence of 1: 12,000¹.

It is subjected to coronary artery disease as in normal population with levocardia and situs solitus².

Literature shows that dextrocardia was first reported by anatomist surgeon Hieronymus Fabricius in 1606³, and Marco Aurelia Severinus in 1643 reported dextrocardia with situs inversus⁴. In adults, mostly it is dextrocardia with atrial and abdominal situs inversus and this is rarely associated with congenital cardiac anomalies.

CABG was first done in dextrocardia in 1980⁵.

Performing surgery when standing on right side of patient in dextrocardia is technically difficult and doing it off pump is like a pimple has grown upon an ulcer. Some issues have to be sorted out during surgery like where should surgeon stand, doing it off pump or on pump, cannulation strategies, conduits for LAD, OM, PDA, which coronary artery is to be anastomosed first or sequence of anastomosis, position of stabilizer etc.

Selection of conduit and configuration of graft is very important in CABG and it becomes very crucial in dextrocardia because now main mass of heart is on right side. RIMA can easily reach upto LAD in this situation; however Kuwata⁶ and chakravarthy⁷ used skeletonised LIMA in situ for LAD.

In most of the case reports and paper presented so far it was shown that one arterial graft, which is usually RIMA for LAD was used and for the rest of coronaries venous grafts were used. Kuwata T et al reported a case where he performed total arterial surgery off pump⁶. We decided to do a total arterial revascularization off pump. RIMA was used as pedicled graft for LAD, and LIMA and RADIAL artery conduits were used as free grafts for OM and PDA. Pancelet did total arterial revascularization with the help of cardiopulmonary bypass⁸.

Usually RIMA is anastomosed to LAD, considering its proximity to rightward LAD.

In dextrocardia, obtuse marginal vessels are more anterior and a conduit with short length can be used, therefore it is more suitable to do total arterial revascularization as they are less prone to kinking than SVGs⁹.

Because of position of the heart in dextrocardia it is preferred to stand on left side of the patient for the coronary anastomosis as it is easy to graft LAD and OM exposed by retracting the heart to left. Few cases are reported in which surgery was done when standing on right side¹⁰ and we found that this surgery can be done with standing on right side without any difficulty.

Texas study showed that in dextrocardia, most surgeons were on the left side, cardiopulmonary bypass was used frequently, and usually one arterial and rest were venous grafts were used¹¹.

When using cardiopulmonary bypass position of aortic arch is very important to place the arterial cannula and usually in dextrocardia it is right aortic arch¹². Presence of SVC draining into coronary sinus has to be checked for venous cannulation and retrograde cardioplegia¹³.

SUMMARY

Dextrocardia poses challenges to surgeons but slight modifications make the grafting easier. Although in our case we did not change the surgeon's position and completed the whole procedure as we do CABG in levocardia without any difficulty. By doing total arterial revascularization without the help of cardiopulmonary bypass we could do the best for the patient in our scenario.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATION

- CABG : Coronary Artery Bypass Grafting
- CPB : Cardiopulmonary Bypass
- CAD : Coronary Artery Disease
- TVD : Triple Vessel Disease
- HRCT : High Resolution Computerized Tomography
- IMA : Internal Mammary Artery
- RIMA : Right Internal Mammary Artery
- LIMA : Left Internal Mammary Artery
- ECG : Electrocardiogram
- LAD : Left Anterior Descending Artery
- OM : Obtuse Marginal
- RCA : Right Coronary Artery
- PDA : Posterior Descending Artery
- ICU : Intensive Care Unit
- SVG : Saphenous Vein Graft
- SVC : Superior Vena Cava

Figure 2: ECG

Figure 1: Chest X-ray

Figure 3: 2D Echo Report

Figure 4a: LAD and Left Circumflex Artery

Figure 4b: LAD and Left Circumflex Artery

Figure 4c: LAD and Left Circumflex Artery

Figure 4d: Right Coronary Artery

Figure 5: Anatomy

Figure 6a: RIMA Harvesting

Figure 6b: RIMA Graft

Figure 6c: RIMA Graft

Figure 6d: LIMA Harvesting

Figure 6e: LIMA

Figure 6f: Left Radial Artery Graft Harvesting

Figure 7: Proximal Anastomosis

Figure 8: LAD Grafting

Figure 9: OM 1 Grafting

Figure 10: PDA Grafting